

Tools for SACRO - User Guide

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1 Introduction and Scope

1.1 What are SACRO tools?

SACRO stands for Semi-automated Checking of Research Outputs. SACRO (or AI-SDC) tools are a group of tools designed to help researchers perform this checking. They include:

- ACRO (python)
- ACRO-R
- SACRO-ML
- SACRO-Viewer

Detailed information on these can be found at <https://sacro-tools.org/>.

1.2 What is in this User Guide?

1.2.1 Tools

This user guide covers two of the tools: SACRO-Viewer and ACRO.

ACRO performs automated checks that look for potential disclosure risks in research outputs. It is a python package providing (a) analytical and statistical functions (mainly lightweight wrappers around Pandas and Statsmodels functions) to generate outputs such as tables, regression models and so on, (b) functionality to check these outputs for disclosure risk, and (c) reports of disclosure risk checks.

Users can then take those ACRO-generated results and load them into SACRO-Viewer.

SACRO-Viewer is a Python wrapper that provides a simple, user-friendly interface for reviewing results produced by ACRO or ACRO-R. The viewer presents the checks in a clear, interactive format, making it easier to look through issues, understand them, and confirm whether the outputs are safe to release.

Together, ACRO and SACRO-Viewer support a straightforward workflow: generate checks with ACRO, review them visually with SACRO-Viewer, record the decision on whether to release outputs, and finally release outputs for download.

1.2.2 Scope and Assumptions

This user guide is intended to complement, not duplicate, the information provided in the official documentation (which can be accessed at the website above). The official documentation covers core features, a detailed API reference, examples and a user guide covering core functions, and basic installation information. This user guide covers:

- Installation of tools (Viewer and ACRO) in Ronin Core for Ubuntu and Windows operating systems
- Quick start to using Viewer in Ronin
- Quick start to using ACRO in Ronin
- High level walk-through of functionality and workflow

It assumes that the reader possesses a basic understanding of their operating system in Ronin Core, as it is not feasible to cover every potential issue or error that may occur during installation or use. It also assumes that users are comfortable using command line tools for installation and are comfortable using Python or R to generate research outputs in e.g. Jupyter notebooks.

The following sections have been prepared to assist users of RONIN in setting up and operating the tools effectively.

2 ACRO installation

Before using the SACRO-Viewer it is necessary to generate outputs from ACRO. In order to install ACRO in a new RONIN virtual machine, follow the steps below. All the commands should be run in the command line.

2.1 Ubuntu

2.1.1 Requirements

Before installing ACRO, check that Python3 and pip3 are installed.

- Check python is installed by executing the following in the command line: **'python3 --version'**. It should return something like **Python 3.12.3**. If not, firstly install Python3.
- Once Python3 is installed, use **'sudo apt install python3-pip'** in the command line to install pip3.

2.1.2 Installing ACRO

To install ACRO directly:

- Run

```
pip install acro
```

To install ACRO within a virtual environment:

- Install **venv** using **'sudo apt install python3-venv'**.
- Create a virtual environment using **'python3 -m venv ~path'**. The virtual environment will be created inside the provided path.
- Activate the virtual environment using **'source ~path/bin/activate'**.
- Once it is activated you should see **'(venv name) ubuntu@yourIP: \$'** on your terminal. Now run **'pip3 install acro'** to install the library. Note that ACRO will be installed only within that virtual environment, so you need to link your project to that venv to use it. For more information about venv in python see the documentation.
- To deactivate the venv and use the regular terminal run **'deactivate'**.

2.2 Windows

2.2.1 Requirements

- Check that Python and pip are installed.

- Check for Python using `'python --version'` or `'py --version'` in the command line. It should return something like **Python 3.12.3**. If not, install Python from the official website or the Microsoft Store.
- Pip usually comes with Python, but you can verify it using `'pip --version'` in the command line.

2.2.2 Installing ACRO

To install ACRO directly:

- Run

```
pip install acro
```

To install ACRO within a virtual environment:

- Create a virtual environment using `'python -m venv path\to\env'`. The virtual environment will be created in the provided path.
- Activate the virtual environment:
 - On Command Prompt: `'path\to\env\Scripts\activate'`
 - On PowerShell: `'path\to\env\Scripts\Activate.ps1'`
- Once it is activated you should see something like `'(env) C:\Users\YourName'` on your terminal. Now run `'pip install acro'` to install the library. Note that **acro** will be installed only within that virtual environment, so you need to link your project to that venv to use it.
- To deactivate the venv and use the regular terminal run `'deactivate'`.

3 ACRO Quick Start

Overview

ACRO is a Python library designed to support statistical disclosure control (SDC) alongside the standard data analysis tasks typically performed in research projects. It enables users to apply disclosure controls in a transparent and reproducible manner while working with sensitive data.

Installation

ACRO can be installed like any other Python package using pip:

```
pip install acro
```

For more details, see section 2.

Importing and Initialization

Once installed, ACRO can be imported and initialized as follows:

```
from acro import ACRO
acro = ACRO()
```

Instance Configuration

The `ACRO()` constructor accepts two optional parameters:

- `suppress`: A boolean flag indicating whether automatic suppression should be applied (default: `False`).
- `config`: A string specifying the name of the `.yaml` configuration file that defines ACRO's settings (default: `default`).

3.1 Configuration

To configure ACRO and change the thresholds based on which values are flagged as risky and get suppressed, you need to do it directly through a configuration file. The configuration file needs to be a `.yaml` file and should be placed inside the `/acro` folder. To locate the `'acro'` folder simply run:

```
pip show acro
```

and look for the `'Location'`. It should look something like `'...../python3.13/site-packages'`, and in that case it would be inside `'/site-packages'`. You can also change the values in the existing `'default.yaml'` (see as example) file which is located inside `/acro` as well. The variables that need to be inside the configuration file are:

- `safe_threshold` → *Frequency threshold*
- `safe_dof_threshold` → *Degrees of freedom threshold*
- `safe_nk_n` → *n parameter for n, k test: largest n values account for less than k% of the total*

- `safe_nk_k` → *k* parameter for *n*, *k* test: largest *n* values account for less than *k*% of the total
- `safe_ratio_p` → parameter for *p*-ration test: sum of smallest *N-2* values accounts for at least *p*% of largest
- `check_missing_values` (Boolean) → *refuse checking for missing values*
- `survival_safe_threshold` → *Frequency threshold for survival tables and plots*
- `zeros_are_disclosive` (Boolean) → *Consider zeros to be disclosive*

3.2 Generating Outputs

After initializing and configuring `acro`, and once the data are loaded as a pandas dataframe, everything is set to start the data analysis and SDC. Some of the main ACRO class functions used in a typical workflow are:

- `crosstab()` → *Computes a frequency table of columns*
- `pivot_table()` → *Creates a spreadsheet-style pivot table as a DataFrame*
- `hist()` → *Creates a histogram for a single column*
- `logit()` → *Fits a simple logistic regression model*
- `finalise()` → *Finalizes ACRO and generates a folder with all the produced outputs*

For more information about the supported functions see the documentation.

Once all the desired outputs have been produced, `acro` needs to be finalised using `finalise()` in order for all the outputs to be saved and the output folder to be generated. The destination and the name of the output folder should be specified within the `'path'` parameter of `'finalise()'`. Then, the output folder can be forwarded to the entity that is responsible to approve or reject the publication of the outputs, who can use SACRO-Viewer to evaluate them.

3.3 Working Example

```
#importing relevant libraries
import pandas as pd
from acro import ACRO

#initialising an acro instance that will suppress outputs and is configured
#through default.yaml
acro = ACRO(suppress=True,config='default')

#reading the data from a .csv file
data=pd.read_csv('data.csv')

#creating a frequency crosstab for Column1 and Column2
acro.crosstab(data['Column1'],data['Column2'])

#Finalising acro. The output folder will be generated inside the working directory
#and will be named as 'output'
acro.finalise(path='./output')
```

4 SACRO Viewer Installation

To download SACRO-Viewer, visit the official GitHub page [here](#) and download the latest release build for the desired operating system.

4.1 Linux Ubuntu

To install and run SACRO-Viewer in a new RONIN Ubuntu virtual machine you have two options.

Option 1:

- open firefox by running **'run firefox &'**.
- download the SACRO viewer package.
- run **'sudo dpkg -i sacro_0.1.0_amd64.deb'** inside /Downloads/SACRO-0.1.0-linux-build to install the .deb file. You will get a warning about dependencies.
- run **'sudo apt-get install -f'** to install all the dependencies.

Option 2:

- open firefox by running **'run firefox &'**.
- download the SACRO viewer package.
- run **'sudo apt install gnome-software'** to install software-center.
- right click on sacro_0.1.0_amd64.deb and then **'open with another application → Software Install → Install'** to install it.
- Software-center will require the user password. By default, the system doesn't have a password, so you need to set one up through the terminal by running **'sudo passwd'** and choosing a password. Then you can download sacro through software-center.
- now you can run SACRO viewer like a regular app.

4.2 Windows

To install and run SACRO-Viewer in a new RONIN Windows virtual machine:

- Download the SACRO-Viewer package for windows.
- Extract the contents from the downloaded .zip file.
- Double click the **sacro 0.1.0.msi** file to install.
- You will get a windows security warning because the executable is not from an authorised provider. Press **'more info→Run anyway'**.

5 SACRO Viewer Quick Start

To start using SACRO-Viewer, find the application in your system and double click on it. Then, select the folder that contains the ACRO output files and press ‘Open’. SACRO-Viewer comes with a sample set of ACRO outputs that is inside the /**outputs** folder which can be used as a first test. After selecting the folder, the homepage should look like ‘Figure 5.1’ (shown for sample ACRO outputs bundled with the viewer):

Figure 5.1: SACRO-Viewer Homepage

On the left side of the window, you can view all the files that are included in the selected folder.

- SACRO-Viewer highlights with **red** the outputs that have not passed the outputs checks of ACRO and require further investigation.
- Highlighted with **blue** are the outputs that have passed the tests performed by ACRO .
- Highlighted with **purple** are the files that have not been produced by ACRO and are not accepted by SACRO-Viewer.

It must be mentioned that SACRO-Viewer does not save the user’s progress in comments and approvals, so if you close the application you will need to start from scratch again.

5.1 ACRO parameters

The ‘ACRO risk profile’ section describes the parameters that ACRO has been initialized with in order to produce these outputs. By using different parameters in ACRO, the outputs produced

could be different, as certain outputs could potentially fail to pass the tests using different thresholds and vice versa.

6 SACRO Viewer Usage

When selecting an output as seen in ‘Figure 6.1’ and ‘6.2’ , SACRO-Viewer will display the details of the checks conducted by ACRO and the researcher’s comments. The user of SACRO-Viewer has to analyze the details of the output and decide whether the results are safe to be published, by approving or rejecting them using the relevant buttons and commenting on the decision inside the relevant box. When the user’s decision is different from the one made by ACRO, for example when the user wants to approve an output that has been rejected by ACRO, that can only be done by providing a relevant comment on the decision. When a comment has been added, SACRO-Viewer will allow the user to select the approve button as seen in ‘Figure6.3’.

After making a decision for every output contained in the folder, SACRO-Viewer will enable the ‘Release and Download’ button as seen in ‘Figure6.4’ , which will generate and download a file that contains the decisions made for each output along with the comments. That file can be sent or discussed with the researcher, in order to finalize the results that will leave the secure data environment and consequently be shared with third parties.

Figure 6.1: SACRO-Viewer Review of an Output part 1

Figure 6.2: SACRO-Viewer Review of an Output part 2

Figure 6.3: SACRO-Viewer when approved button is enabled

Figure 6.4: SACRO-Viewer when download button is enabled

7 SACRO Viewer Output

Once the 'Release and download' button is clicked, a page like 'Figure 7.1' will appear which will give you the option to download the approved outputs and the review summary within the Ronin environment. 'Figure 7.1' and 'Figure 7.2' are examples of the downloaded files.

The review summary is a .txt file that includes for each output the approval or rejection by both ACRO and the SACRO-Viewer user, along with the comments made by the user for each output. The point of the file is to give the researcher a brief explanation of why an output has been approved or rejected, and possibly include other comments regarding the actions that need to be taken from his side.

The review summary file can be shared with the researcher within the project space, who can then proceed with publishing only the approved outputs via standard egress procedures, and/or make changes to the rejected outputs in ACRO for re-evaluation.

Figure 7.1: Download outputs page

```

Terminal
# Review summary
Fix the rejected outputs and resend for further discussion

## crosstab_fail
ACRO status: fail
Reviewer status: approved
Fine to be published by me if you remove those rows

## crosstab_fail_2
ACRO status: fail
Reviewer status: rejected
I cannot approve that

## pivot_table_success
ACRO status: pass
Reviewer status: approved
Approved by me, nothing to change

## ols_pass
ACRO status: pass
Reviewer status: approved
Approved by me, nothing to change

## olsr_pass
ACRO status: pass
Reviewer status: approved
Approved by me, nothing to change

## probit_pass
ACRO status: pass
Reviewer status: approved
Approved by me, nothing to change

## logit_pass
1,0-1 Top

```

Figure 7.2: Summary outputs

‘Approved outputs’ as seen in ‘Figure 7.3’, is .zip file that contains all the outputs that the SACRO-Viewer user had to review along with the review summary file which is described above. That .zip file can be shared with the researcher and also it can be kept in file for future use or referencing.

Name	Size	Type	Modified
logit_pass_0.csv	277 bytes	CSV docu...	03 December 20...
logit_pass_1.csv	126 bytes	CSV docu...	03 December 20...
ols_pass_0.csv	319 bytes	CSV docu...	03 December 20...
ols_pass_1.csv	123 bytes	CSV docu...	03 December 20...
ols_pass_2.csv	144 bytes	CSV docu...	03 December 20...
olsr_pass_0.csv	319 bytes	CSV docu...	03 December 20...
olsr_pass_1.csv	127 bytes	CSV docu...	03 December 20...
olsr_pass_2.csv	144 bytes	CSV docu...	03 December 20...
pivot_table_success_0.csv	178 bytes	CSV docu...	03 December 20...
probit_pass_0.csv	278 bytes	CSV docu...	03 December 20...
probit_pass_1.csv	127 bytes	CSV docu...	03 December 20...
summary.txt	1.3 kB	plain text ...	18 November 20...

Figure 7.3: Approved Outputs